

COMPUTER SCIENCES

INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR TESTING STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE USING GAMIFICATION ELEMENTS

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Abstract

The article considers the essence of gamification in education, which turned from entertainment into a means of increasing students' motivation to study and attracting them to active participation in the learning process. To increase students' motivation and interest in learning, gamification involves the use of game elements, such as levels, achievements, points, virtual awards, etc. Gamification in education helps students enjoy their achievements. The work describes the author's web-oriented system of testing known students in the subject area "Software engineering and programming". The system uses elements of gamification.

Keywords: gamification in education, software engineering, database, learning content, web-based system for testing, hierarchical model.

Introduction

Gamification is a concept that demonstrates the use of game-based practices in non-game environments. Gamification is used in various areas of human activity (e.g., education, professional activity, leisure).

The essence of gamification in education is to make learning fun and engage students in the learning process [1]. To increase student motivation and interest in learning, gamification involves the use of game elements such as levels, achievements, points, virtual rewards, etc.

Gamification in education is based on positive reinforcement theory, which states that desired behavior can be reinforced by positive consequences. This could include providing virtual rewards for academic success. This approach to learning helps students experience satisfaction from their accomplishments [2].

Gamification in education has several benefits, including:

- increasing student motivation to learn (students are more interested in the process if it resembles a game);

- increasing student engagement in learning;
- ensuring more effective learning (using game elements, tasks and exercises can be developed that will help students more deeply understand and remember the course material);
- increasing the competitiveness and engagement of online courses (courses with gamification elements can be more attractive to students, especially those seeking interactive and fun ways to learn) [3].

Gamification is applicable to various types and forms of learning. For example, gamification can involve the creation of online games or board games that help students learn the course material. In professional training, gamification can be used when learning new technologies or procedures [4].

Gamification can help engage students with different learning styles. For example, students who are more interested in learning when there is competition and play prefer learning that includes elements of gamification [5].

However, gamification is not a universal solution to all learning problems. There are also negative aspects

to using gamification, such as decreased interest in learning if the educational game becomes too difficult or unpleasant for students [6]. Furthermore, gamification requires specific training and effort from instructors and online course developers. Therefore, for gamification to be effective, so-called individualized gamification should be implemented. That is:

- consider the needs and characteristics of each specific group of students;
- consider the needs and characteristics of each student;
- develop reasonable rules and a reward system;
- use tools that provide adequate feedback and analysis of success [7].

Gamification in education is a useful tool for increasing motivation and learning effectiveness. Gamification helps engage students in learning, increase their interest and motivation for learning [8]. It is important to ensure a balance between gamification and traditional teaching methods. In this case, it is necessary to take into account the needs and characteristics of students, and ensure the competent use of gamification to achieve maximum efficiency and effectiveness of learning [9].

Gamification is increasingly widespread in both offline and online learning. Students earn various badges for completing tasks and are placed on a leaderboard that displays each student's ranking in real time. This approach encourages students to achieve their learning goals and earn more points.

Training and testing students learning programming languages and software development environments have long been integrated into the online world. Numerous platforms offer both training and testing tools. One such platform, **w3schools**, combines training and testing for various programming languages. Each section of educational content is followed by a short assignment, which is assessed for correct completion. When logging into this system, in addition to testing, students are awarded points for completing assignments, and the number of completed assignments is calculated. **w3schools** maintains a balance between the direct provision of educational content (training) and testing. The **SoloLearn** platform allows students to determine their level of knowledge only after completing each topic (or block of topics). Students are awarded badges for achievements in various topics they have successfully mastered, as well as experience points for completing assignments, reflecting their level of knowledge.

Research results

We will describe our own software development – web-based system for testing students' knowledge in the subject area “Software Engineering and Programming”. The system incorporates gamification elements.

Development of the system began with the selection of objects that would serve as sections when creating testing blocks. These blocks were defined by the areas of software development and software engineering. These objects, in particular, included: program code in C-like languages (C, C++, C#); web-oriented code (Ja-

vaScript); web-oriented server-side code (PHP); databases (SQL, MySQL); mobile application development (Java).

For each of these topics, common features were identified across all areas. Testing involves the use of common and specific features. For common features, identical questions were created, defining such domain concepts as:

- code file name extension ();
- function declaration syntax;
- variable declaration syntax;
- declaration of variables of different types;
- syntax for creating urgent variables;
- for loop structure;
- while loop structure;
- function call;
- passing function parameters;
- class creation;
- class constructor syntax;
- access modifiers in classes;
- static class methods;
- calling a static class method;
- declaring a class object;
- class inheritance declaration syntax;
- declaring a dictionary as a data type.

Specific features can be reflected, for example, in question blocks related to databases. For databases, the following question blocks were created: database creation syntax; table creation syntax; primary key declaration syntax with increment; foreign key descriptions; field declaration with automatic increment when adding a record to a table; data types; and table view creation. For programming languages, specific features were reflected in the following question blocks, for example: structure declaration syntax (C, C++, C#); associative array (for JavaScript).

The developed system identified the following:

- software development areas (testing subject areas);
- training content topics;
- question groups (blocks) corresponding to training content topics.

Database was developed for data storage, which will store software development areas, topics, and questions related to topics.

Information about spheres is stored in a table containing the following information: the sphere code (which is independent of users, as it is the primary key) and the sphere name.

Information about topics is stored in a table containing: a unique topic code, the sphere code to which the topic belongs, the topic name, and its type. The question table stores data about each specific question. It contains: the question code, the code of the topic to which the question is associated, and the question name, the answer.

All of these tables can be represented as hierarchical model, where the top level reflects areas, the second level reflects topics, and the bottom level reflects questions on a specific topic within the subject area.

To store user testing results, the following table was created:

- student code, login, and password;

- student assessment results table, containing:
 - testing code;
 - student code;
 - code of the area in which the testing was conducted;
 - number of points;
 - testing time.

The developed web-based system provides access to testing knowledge of programming writing. The user first registers/logs in the system, after which they can begin testing in one of the five areas implemented in the system. Questions are presented to the student one at a time for the corresponding area.

After receiving answers (from students) to all questions, the system calculates points (according to the number of correct answers per topic) and determines the student's rating for that topic. All this data is entered into the database along with the student's testing time.

The system is based on hierarchical model, in which each area of the "Software Engineering and Programming" subject area has multiple paths that link to topics within these areas, which are their topics. Each topic has multiple outputs that link to the corresponding test questions. Using hierarchical model allows the system to be scalable to any task, adapting areas, topics, and questions to specific subject area (with its general and specific characteristics).

The system allows access to adding, editing, and deleting any level of the model, so modifications can be made quickly, allowing for the rapid creation of new task blocks. Each of these areas has its own sublevels, which are expanded by clicking the arrow indicating the downward direction. This will reveal all questions on the topic entered into the system.

The system uses gamification elements. An authorized user can access the test by clicking on the names of the corresponding blocks on the system's main page. At first, it seems like nothing out of the ordinary, but that's until the first assignments corresponding to the chosen subject area are completed.

After studying the section's educational content, the student's progress on the test assignments is displayed on the system's main page. This progress reflects (as percentage) the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_j} v_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_j} mv_i} \\
 &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_j} v_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{n_j} mv_i}
 \end{aligned}$$

where Pr_j is the student's progress in the j -th section of the course (an indicator of the student's mastery of the educational content of the j -th section of the subject area (course));

j is the course section number, $j = 1, \dots, k$, k is the number of sections in the course;

v_i is the number of points received by the student for completing the i -th assignment ($i = 1, \dots, n_j$) of the j -th section of the course;

n_j is the number of assignments provided by the author to test the student's mastery of the educational content of the j -th section of the course;

$\sum_{i=1}^{n_j} v_i$ – the sum of the points received by the student for completing all n_j assignments in the j -th section of the course;

mv_i – the maximum number of points the student could have received for correctly completing the i -th assignment ($i = 1, \dots, n_j$) in the j -th section of the course;

(mv_i is assigned by the test author for this i -th assignment in the j -th section of the course)

$\sum_{i=1}^{n_j} mv_i$ – the sum of the maximum number of points the student could have received for correctly completing all n_j assignments for the j -th section of the course.

After calculating the Pr_j indicator, the system displays the following indicators to the student:

- the number of points earned by the student (based on the maximum possible number for this section (or block of the section));
- the percentage of correct answers provided by the student;
- the time it took to complete the test; the more tasks completed, the greater the overall progress.

The system will also provide other messages to the student. Upon achieving some success in completing the tests, the student will begin to receive other messages:

- in addition to messages reflecting the student's overall progress, a percentage of how successfully the student completed the test (compared to other students) is also displayed;
- the average test completion time and the student's actual test completion time (displayed in a special color chart: green if the student completes the test faster, red if the student completes the tasks more slowly), with a notification to the student about how quickly or slowly they completed the test.

Gamification is manifested here in the special display of the student's progress and their speed of completing the test tasks. Other elements that gamify the learning (testing) process are used and are displayed on the test task page. The task page displays messages such as the name of the field, the name of the topic, and the current question of the test. Gamification elements are presented here in the form of:

- clock displaying the time allotted for testing;
- notification of the number of tasks already completed.

In addition, new gamification elements are introduced when answering test questions, encouraging students to complete tasks more quickly and accurately. These elements include, in particular, displaying the level of correctness of the corresponding fields of the test tasks and messages to the student, whose test score depends on the correct completion of individual tasks.

If the student answers correctly, they are shown an encouraging message, which can vary (as it is selected from the corresponding table in the system database, which stores phrases that are semantically synonymous). A randomly selected synonymous phrase from this table is presented to the student.

If the student answers the test questions incorrectly or partially correctly, they are presented with a

different message, which will have the following meaning: "Answer incorrect"/"Answer partially correct." Messages will also be selected from a table of synonym messages (synonyms are selected based on semantics).

Fig. 1 shows the window for the first subject area (course), which displays all the topics for which the student will be provided test questions.

Figure 1. Window displaying test topics for the first subject area.

Each topic has its own subtopics. The testing system uses gamification elements, which are applied at different stages of testing (answering test questions). An authorized user can access testing by selecting the corresponding question sets on the system's main page.

After studying the educational content of a section and answering the test questions for that section, the student receives the following metrics on the system's main page:

- progress Pr_j (j is the course section number, $j = 1, \dots, k$, k is the number of sections in the course) for completing the corresponding test tasks for the j -th section;

- number of points scored (out of the possible points for this question set);
- percentage of correct answers; time required to complete the test;
- average time to complete the test (answering test questions for this section);
- place in the ranking list of all students taking the test in this section.

The more tasks a student completes correctly, the greater their overall progress. The assignment page (Fig. 2) displays a block displaying the field name, topic name, and current test question.

Figure 2. Test page window for the subject area "Software Engineering"

Using gamification elements, the student is shown:

- test time (student, average, best);
- number of tasks already completed;
- motivational messages to help complete tasks faster and more accurately;
- graphic (colored) display of the level of accuracy in completing the relevant test fields.

The purpose of the developed software product is to test the knowledge of students studying programming. Using gamification in this learning process creates a desire in the student to earn more points, achieve positive results, complete them in less time, and receive positive feedback (positive messages) from the system.

Initially, the student doesn't feel driven to achieve the best results, but as they complete each set of questions, their progress steadily increases, motivating them to achieve the highest reward (e.g., all correct answers, 100% completion rate, the highest score, and the fastest time among other students). To achieve all these rewards, the student must practice, for example, memorizing which answers were correct to a specific question to achieve the best result in the shortest time.

To begin working in the system, students must register or log in. To do this, click the button "Login" or the section "Log in to view progress" and proceed to the registration/login page. Here, students must enter their login information to register or log in. They must enter their username and password in the appropriate fields and click one of the two buttons on this page. When clicking the button "Register", the student's information will be checked to ensure it is correct and that they are not already registered in the system. If an error occurs during registration, the student will receive a response message. If the student clicks the button "Authorize", the system will check whether they are registered in the system.

After registration/authorization, the student is automatically redirected to the main page of the system, where their name and current progress will be displayed. Under each topic block, it will be indicated that the student has not yet taken the test for that topic/section.

The student can now take the test. To begin testing, the student clicks the image (title) of one of the question blocks in the corresponding subject area "Software Engineering and Programming." After this, the student will automatically be redirected to a page displaying the actual test questions. For ease of use and to make the interface easier to understand, this page also displays the following elements:

- time elapsed since the start of the test (in **minutes: seconds** format);
- name of the testing area;
- current question number and total number of questions;
- question category (displayed on the main page under each area);
- name (wording) of the question to be answered;
- answer entry field (it is partially filled in, and only the missing sections need to be filled in);
- button to confirm the question answer.

The answer entry field consists of fixed text that the student can edit and a field for entering part of the answer. Each answer field contains only one word (one code element). For the question "A function that returns an integer is called main and has no parameters," the result is `int main() {}`. There are four elements, but the input field already has parentheses at the end, so the three elements are split between the three fields, yielding the result (Fig. 3).

Тестування ІПЗ Делант Вихід

Час тесту: 00:13 Код на С подібних мовах (C++, C#) Питання №3/22

Категорія: Синтаксис оголошення функції

Питання: Як оголошується функція, яка повертає ціле число, має назву main та не має параметрів

int main () {}

Підтвердити

Figure 3. Example of filling in answer fields

Thus, the answer resembles program code, which is written separately in each input field. To confirm the answer, the student clicks the "Confirm" button, after which they are presented with the test results for the current question.

If the student confirms their answer, the system colors the correct blocks of code green and the incorrect

blocks red. The error in Fig. 4 was intentionally created to demonstrate this coloring. Thus, the student answers the test questions (tasks) and receives their points. After answering all the questions, the student receives their test result (in points) and the test time.

Тестування ІПЗ Делант Вихід

Час тесту: 00:20 Код на С подібних мовах (C++, C#) Питання №3/22

Категорія: Синтаксис оголошення функції

Питання: Як оголошується функція, яка повертає ціле число, має назву main та не має параметрів

int main () {}

Наступне питання

Figure 4. Window after the student confirms their answer

After completing the test, the student can: return to the main page by clicking the "Continue" button to continue testing (with a different set of questions); complete the testing process, receive the results, and log out. When returning to the previous page, the student sees several new sets of questions, gamification elements, etc. (for example, the pre-test result).

The student also sees a display of their entire test results for the entire subject area. The student can see all their statistics and compare them with those of other students (Fig. 5). The first display shows the overall progress, where 100% indicates the student's answers were completely correct in all tests.

Figure 5. Window with the final test results (statistics) for student receiving only "excellent" grades

Conclusions

This paper analyzes existing approaches to developing testing systems with gamification elements. A system for testing student knowledge in the subject area of "Software Engineering and Programming" was developed, utilizing gamification elements. The developed knowledge testing system will contribute to increased student motivation and improve the overall effectiveness of the educational process (specifically, testing).

The system utilizes hierarchical model of the main components of a subject area (course), where each area of software development has multiple paths that link to topics subordinate to these areas and are their constituent components. Each topic has multiple outputs leading to test questions (question blocks).

The hierarchical model allows the system to be scalable to any assignment, adapting areas, topics, and questions to a specific section (topic or topic block).

The developed system will help students with varying levels of knowledge and skills receive a personalized approach to learning, improving their understanding and retention of the material.

References

1. Gamification in Education – Edutopia. Available at: <https://www.edutopia.org/topic/gamification>
2. Mauruner, O. (2019). Gamification in Management and Other Non-Game Contexts—Understanding Game Elements, Motivation, Reward Systems, and User Types. Open Journal of Business and Management, 07(04):1815-1830. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2019.74125>
3. Werbach, K., Hunter, D. (2012). For the Win: How Game Thinking Can Revolutionize Your Business. Philadelphia: Wharton Digital Press, 2012. 264 p.
4. Gamification – Gamasutra. Available at: <https://www.gamasutra.com/topic/gamification>

5. Dangpraserti, Sawanan (2023). The impact of gamification on creative and innovative skills of graduate students. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, vol.101, № 8, pp. 3077-3087.

6. Zichermann G., Cunningham C. (2011). *Gamification by Design: Implementing Game Mechanics in Web and Mobile Apps*. Sebastopol: O'Reilly Media, 2011. 208 p.

7. Yu-kai Chou: Gamification & Behavioral Design. Available at: <https://yukaichou.com/>

8. 6 Examples of Gamification Software Technology. Available at: <https://spinify.com/blog/examples-of-gamification-in-software-technology>

9. Andrzej Marczewski (2017). Really Simple Gamification – Randomness Available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/really-simple-gamification-randomness-andrzej-marczewski>